

RoguePlots_UBI-24-TE: This pdf contains the RoguePlots created for the 24 fossils resulted from the unconstrained Bayesian analysis for 24 fossils using total evidence data (UBI-24-TE).

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X_Archaeanthus_linnenbergeri

X_Archaestella_verticillatus

X_Bertilanthus_scanicus

X_Canrightia_resinifera

X_Florissantia_quilchenensis

